

AC-DC Cuk Converter: A State-of-the-Art topological review

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ABSTRACT

AC-DC converters, which transform alternating current (AC) into controlled direct current (DC), are key instruments for systems requiring stable and efficient power conversion. Among various AC-DC topologies, the Cuk converter topology is increasingly used for power factor correction (PFC) applications, enabling efficient power conversion for various industrial and household devices. Despite its growing adoption in AC-DC applications, the existing literature does not thoroughly examine the technical aspects of the modern Cuk topologies. This paper seeks to fill this gap by comprehensively analyzing recent topological advancements in AC-DC Cuk converters, encompassing their categorizations, performance attributes, and applications. The evaluation and review of the prominent converter topologies have been summarized in a tabular format, presenting essential converter metrics, including component counts, operation modes, isolation and rectification styles, power ratings, power factor, and total harmonic distortion (THD). The paper aims to provide valuable insights for researchers, design engineers, and manufacturers through technical comparison and topology evaluation. In addition, the related technical issues and challenges regarding selecting a suitable converter topology are addressed in this article.

1. Introduction

Alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC) power conversion has widespread use in modern technology. AC-DC converters, known as rectifiers, are typically designed to transform AC power into a stable DC output suitable for operating electronic devices. However, conventional uncontrolled rectifiers have notable drawbacks, including poor power quality due to injected current harmonics, which lead to voltage distortion and a low power factor on the input side. To mitigate these issues, specialized AC-DC converters are employed as power factor correction (PFC) converters. A PFC converter incorporates additional circuitry to control its waveforms and correct the power factor. These converters are utilized in various applications like adjustable-speed drives, switch-mode power supplies, uninterrupted power supplies, and nonconventional energy sources such as solar energy, electric vehicles, energy storage systems, electroplating, welding units, etc. [1].

Most PFC converters utilize boost [2,3,4,5,6], buck-boost [7,8] or fly-back derived topologies [9]. Among these topologies, boost PFCs are the

most popular thanks to their cost effectiveness, high voltage gain, and ability to maintain continuous input current [10]. On the contrary, buck PFCs are typically used in low-power applications where step-down operation is required. Because of the inherent dead zones, buck PFC has a limited power factor (PF) and high current distortion, which makes it challenging to fulfill current harmonic criteria. As a result, the buck converter is rarely used in PFC applications because of its discontinuous input current, leading to control loss [8]. Both boost or buck converters are unsuitable for applications requiring both step-up and step-down functionality. In such applications, buck-boost converters capable of providing variable voltage gain are used [11].

The Cuk converter belongs to the buck-boost converter family and can handle both step-up and step-down operations, allowing it to handle a wide range of input and output requirements [12]. A key feature of the Cuk converter is its use of two inductors and two capacitors, which results in continuous input and output currents and significantly reduces current and voltage ripple compared to conventional buck-boost converters. It leads to improved electromagnetic interference (EMI)

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performance, often without additional input filters. These features make Cuk topologies suitable for applications with high-quality power that needs to be delivered [13].

2. Related works and Motivations

The notable review works on AC-DC and PFC converters are summarized in Table 1. Several reviews have focused on boost PFC converters, which remain the most widely adopted topology for power factor correction. In comparison, fewer review studies have been conducted on buck, buck-boost, and Cuk converters. Among these, buck converters are typically excluded from commercial PFC applications due to several drawbacks discussed earlier. However, the popularity of Cuk converters has increased over time. After conducting an extensive literature review, we identified a brief review paper that focuses exclusively on DC-DC Cuk converters [14]. This paper focuses on and compares only the conventional and bidirectional DC-DC Cuk converter variants. In [15], the AC-DC Cuk rectifier has been compared with Flyback and interleaved single-ended primary inductor (SEPIC) converters. Consequently, this study lacks a comprehensive taxonomy and does not provide detailed technical comparisons. The limitations of both these works are summarized in Table 2.

This study presents a systematic and comprehensive review of Cuk-based AC-DC converters to address the identified research gap in this domain. With the rapid proliferation of Cuk PFC converters across industrial and consumer electronics, researchers, industry professionals, and design engineers increasingly require a consolidated framework to evaluate and compare emerging topologies. This review simplifies this process by offering a structured analysis of advancements in Cuk converter designs, enabling stakeholders to assess their technical merits, limitations, and suitability for specific application-based adoption.

The key contributions and objectives of this paper are summarized as follows:

Mitigation of Research Gaps: This paper addresses a significant gap in the literature by providing an in-depth analysis of contemporary AC-DC Cuk converter topologies through a comprehensive synthesis of recent developments.

Evaluation of Merits and Limitations: A systematic classification of Cuk converter topologies is introduced based on operational modes, rectification methods, isolation, number of phases, and power levels, enabling a clearer understanding of their advantages and drawbacks.

Collaborative Information Platform: The review offers a clear and organized presentation of information and data, serving as a valuable resource for researchers, design engineers, and converter manufacturers to select the most suitable Cuk PFC circuit tailored to specific user load requirements.

3. Operation of AC-DC Cuk converter

A conventional AC-DC Cuk converter functions through three sequential stages aligned with its power conversion and control mechanisms, as depicted in Fig. 1. The first stage involves rectifying the AC input voltage into DC using either a traditional bridge rectifier or

Table 1
Existing reviews and literature surveys on different AC-DC / PFC converter topologies.

AC-DC Power Factor Converters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review on AC-DC and PFC converters [15,16] Single-phase AC-DC PFC converter [1,17] Three phase AC-DC and PFC converter[18,19] 						
Boost AC-DC/PFC [20–23]	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>Buck AC-DC/PFC [24]</td> <td>Buck-Boost DC-DC [25]</td> <td>Cuk</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DC-DC [14] AC-DC/PFC [15] </td> </tr> </table>	Buck AC-DC/PFC [24]	Buck-Boost DC-DC [25]	Cuk			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DC-DC [14] AC-DC/PFC [15]
Buck AC-DC/PFC [24]	Buck-Boost DC-DC [25]	Cuk					
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DC-DC [14] AC-DC/PFC [15] 					

Table 2
Limitations and research gaps of the existing review studies on the Cuk converter.

Literature	Limitations and research gaps
P. Anbalagan et al. (2022) [14]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overlooks AC-DC converter topologies. It only focuses on DC-DC Cuk converters. Lacks comprehensiveness: compares DC-DC topologies based on only three criteria: efficiency, duty cycle, and load.
R. Sasikala et al. (2019) [15]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reviews and evaluates AC-DC converters derived from Cuk, Flyback, and interleaved SEPIC topologies. Briefly describes the Cuk rectifier but fails to provide a comprehensive outlook. Lacks a comprehensive taxonomy-compares the converters based on only three criteria: displacement factor, PF, and THD It does not offer an adequate list of references for readers.

Fig. 1. Conventional AC-DC PFC Cuk converter circuit.

semiconductor switches in bridgeless configurations, eliminating passive diode bridges to reduce losses. Following this, the conversion stage performs the core operation through high-frequency switching, dynamically adjusting the output voltage via duty cycle modulation. By leveraging input and output parameters feedback signals, the converter stabilizes the output voltage under fluctuating loads while operating in buck (step-down) or boost (step-up) modes. This stage also optimizes the PF by tailoring switching signals to align the input current with voltage waveforms. Finally, the output stage employs reactive components (inductors, capacitors) and a freewheeling diode to finalize energy transfer, defining the converter’s operational mode (buck/boost) and ensuring smooth DC delivery to the load. These stages enable efficient power conversion, precise voltage regulation, and adaptability to dynamic operational demands. In specific applications, isolation components, such as transformers, can be integrated between the switching stage and the DC-DC converter to enhance safety, reduce noise coupling, or achieve voltage matching [26–28].

The conventional AC-DC Cuk converter operates in four distinct modes, determined by the switch (S) and diode states during each half-cycle of the input voltage waveform (V_1). These modes govern energy transfer, inductor charging/discharging, and output regulation across load resistor R_1 , as illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2(a-d).

Mode 1: During the positive half-cycle, the control signal activates switch S. Diodes D_1 and D_2 rectify the input voltage, allowing current to flow from the AC source through S, inductor L_1 (which stores energy), and the parallel path formed by L_2 , capacitor C_1 , and output capacitor C_2 . Capacitors C_1 and C_2 discharge to support L_2 ’s charging while sustaining current through load R_1 (Fig. 2a).

Mode 2: When S turns OFF, diode D_5 becomes forward-biased, enabling L_1 and the source to charge capacitor C_1 . Simultaneously, inductor L_2 discharges, replenishing C_2 and maintaining uninterrupted current to the load (Fig. 2b).

Mode 3: During the negative half-cycle, S is reactivated. Diodes D_3 and D_4 rectify the input voltage, mirroring Mode 1’s operation but with

Fig. 2. Four Modes of operations of conventional AC-DC PFC Cuk Converter.

reversed polarity. Energy storage components (L_1 , C_1 , C_2) repeat the charging-discharging cycle to stabilize the output (Fig. 2c).

Mode 4: As S turns OFF again, diodes D_3 and D_4 conduct, facilitating the recharge of C_1 by L_1 and the source. It ensures continuous energy delivery to the load via L_2 and C_2 (Fig. 2d).

4. Topological overview and classification

This study categorizes AC-DC Cuk converters into four primary design criteria to streamline comparative analysis: operation mode (continuous vs. discontinuous conduction), rectification type (bridged vs. bridgeless), isolation (isolated vs. non-isolated), and input AC phase (single-phase vs. three-phase). The classification framework, depicted in Fig. 3, organizes these criteria into a hierarchical block diagram, clarifying their relationships and enabling systematic evaluation of converter topologies.

4.1. Conduction modes

The Cuk converter operates in two primary conduction modes: continuous conduction mode (CCM) and discontinuous conduction mode (DCM). These modes form the basis of its operational classification, which is broadly divided into these two categories.

In CCM, the inductor current never falls to zero during the entire switching cycle. It ensures a constant flow of current through the inductors, which minimizes ripple currents. This approach offers several advantages, including smoother operation, reduced output voltage ripple, enhanced system stability, simplified control loop design, and reduced EMI due to the gradual change in current.

Khan et al. [27] utilized the current multiplier method to achieve CCM in a conventional Cuk converter, achieving a near-unity PF and

reducing the THD of the supply current. In [29], Singh & Chaturvedi developed a CCM-operated Cuk converter with a 13.5 V, 20.25 W output, later extending their work [30] to perform a comprehensive analysis of single-phase AC-DC converters for PFC applications in CCM. In [31], a digitally controlled isolated Cuk PFC converter is developed for CCM operation. U. Kamnarn et al. [32] proposed a CCM Cuk converter circuit with a power balance control technique using a proportional-integral (PI) controller capable of significant step load variations. Umamaheswari et al. [33] implemented a three-phase AC-DC Cuk converter using symmetrical component theory to achieve unity PF through extended synchronous detection techniques. Sakib et al. [34] simulated a Cuk AC-DC converter operating in CCM, maintaining an 8 kHz switching frequency at 50 % duty for better performance. In PFC applications, Priya [35] designed a converter for light-emitting diode (LED) driving consisting of diode bridge rectifiers operating in CCM, controlled by a fuzzy voltage controller. Singh et al. [36] integrated a current multiplier with an average current control scheme in CCM, improving PFC converter efficiency. Singh et al. [37] developed a hardware prototype with over 70 % duty cycle in CCM. Gangavarapu et al. [38] proposed a CCM Cuk-derived PFC converter that reduces conduction losses while improving efficiency. Anand et al. [39] introduced a modified dual-output Cuk converter, where the input stage operated in CCM while the output stage worked in DCM. On the other hand, Gaurav Vijay [40] demonstrated a source conditioning diode bridge Continuous AC-DC Cuk converter achieving unity PF through voltage loop and PWM current loop controller. Rahul Pandey et al. [41] designed a bridgeless PFC Cuk converter in CCM for EV applications, and Dhaniyalakshmi et al. [42] proposed a bridgeless PFC system combining CCM and DCM modes implemented on a PIC microcontroller. Amina Hasan Abedin [43] proposed a two-switch voltage-controlled three-phase Cuk rectifier in CCM with fewer components, while Gnanavadi-vel et al. [44] compared PFC performance in an isolated high-frequency single-phase AC-DC Cuk converter under CCM, reducing both switch count and low output voltage. Yutthana Kanthaphayao et al. [45] applied power balance control to a parallel AC to DC converter operating in CCM with the help of voltage loop control and hysteresis controller. Lastly, Nasif Fuad Parash et al. n.d. [46] introduced a novel single-phase AC-DC cascaded boost-Cuk (CBC) converter working in CCM, which lowered THD and improved PF.

In contrast to CCM, during DCM, the inductor current drops to zero during each switching cycle, reducing energy storage requirements and improving efficiency, particularly under light to moderate load conditions [45]. This mode simplifies inductor design due to lower peak current stresses and enables faster transient response. However, DCM operation demands precise duty cycle control to ensure the inductor current fully discharges to zero within each cycle. Despite this, DCM achieves robust closed-loop performance with straightforward single-

Fig. 3. Classifications of AC DC Cuk Converter.

loop control streamlining implementation compared to multi-loop strategies required for CCM.

Several research studies have also been performed on DCM-operated Cuk AC-DC converters. Petrovic et al. [47] provided models for all operating modes of the AC-DC Cuk converter and analyzed various switching systems for linear-time invariant systems. Gangavarapu et al. [48] introduced a three-phase diode-bridge AC-DC Cuk converter operating in discontinuous output inductor current mode (DOICM) using a voltage control loop consisting of three switches to achieve low THD and high PF. Another comprehensive analysis by Singh et al. [30] offered a detailed analysis of single-phase PFC Cuk converter configurations and control strategies applicable in both CCM and DCM. Thanigasankaran et al. [49] proposed a PFC bridgeless Cuk converter in DCM using two switches, and P. R Ajeesh et al. [50] simulated a bridgeless single-semiconductor PFC Cuk converter in DCM with Matlab-Simulink. Bodetto et al. [51] proposed a high-order PFC converter in DCM for low-power applications, using a PI controller that offers an EMI input filter to fulfill harmonic standards. Hossain et al. [52] analyzed the comparative performance of diode rectifiers, open-loop Cuk rectifiers, and closed-loop Cuk rectifiers implementing the closed-loop control in the digital domain. Another voltage loop-controlled AC-DC single switch Cuk converter was proposed by Kumar et al. [53] in D, which got PF up to 0.99 and an efficiency of over 80 %. Singh et al. [54] developed a high-frequency isolated AC-DC Cuk converter in DCM for PMSM drives using a DSP converter and later introduced a Cuk-fed BLDC converter with voltage control in DICM for air conditioning systems; also proposed and simulated a PMBLDCM drive in MATLAB-Simulink [55]. Narula et al. [26] proposed a bridgeless AC-DC Cuk converter in D to achieve a unity PF and minimize EMI in welding power supply applications. Noor et al. [56] presented a bridgeless PFC Cuk converter that reduces circulating current losses and maximum current stress by reconfiguring the input diodes in DCM. Another research work by Thanigasankaran et al. [49] designed an interleaved negative output Cuk converter operating from 90–260 V, improving power quality and reducing THD in DCM with a PI controller. Valan Rajkumar et al. [57] and Kumar et al. [53] developed simplified DCM topologies with fewer switches, using hysteresis current and voltage loop controls. Further contributions include Sree Vidhya et al. [58] who designed a flyback AC-DC diode-bridge three-phase Cuk converter in DCM; Singh et al. [37] proposed a bridgeless three-phase AC-DC Cuk converter for wind energy systems; and Pomilio et al. [59] who developed an isolated Cuk topology in DICM operating at 50 kHz with PWM control. Another research work was done by B. Singh [60] on an isolated high-frequency PFC-corrected Cuk converter in DCM operation with a low power rating of 20.25 W and output voltage of 13.5 V. Yang et al. [61], Gangavarapu et al. [38], and Govindaraj et al. [62] focused on DCM designs offering reduced switch count, lower losses, and simpler control strategies and prototyped by Shamel et al. [63] provides soft switching operation by only a single switch and operates in DCM, giving low THD and high PF. Lin et al. [64] proposed a bridgeless Cuk converter with three operation stages in one switching period. When the power switches are on, two conduct the input cycle, and one conduct the output cycle. Babaei et al. [65] proposed a high step-down bridgeless Cuk converter in DCM based on the switched inductor network, which provides high step-down voltage gain with a longer duty cycle. Three AC-DC Cuk Converters in DCM were designed and analyzed in papers [66–68]. Operating in DCM, circuits became simple, consisting of fewer semiconductor components, reduced switching losses, high efficiency, less THD, and greater PF have been achieved. Radha Kushwaha [69] proposed a bridgeless DCM Cuk converter for electric vehicle chargers, achieving improved power quality, zero-current switching, and low diode recovery losses. The experiments of Guilherme M. Soares [56] on a Cuk-based LED driver operating in DCM at 220 V AC and 60 Hz frequency maintaining current control without complex techniques. Sabzali et al. [70], Govindaraj et al. [62], and Gupta et al. [71] advanced single-phase and bridgeless DCM Cuk converter designs for unity PF. This circuit eliminated the drawbacks of conventional Cuk AC-DC

converters, achieving zero circulating current through an antiparallel diode and zero loop current. Varshney et al. [72] applied DCM to electric bike battery charging systems, achieving low THD at a 75 kHz switching frequency using fundamental components.

4.2. Rectification style

AC to DC can be rectified through conventional methods such as diode bridges or unconventional combinations involving switches and diodes. The reviewed papers can be categorized into two groups based on the rectification process: diode bridge and bridgeless configurations.

A significant number of research works have employed full-wave diode bridge rectifiers for AC to DC conversion [27,29,30,34,35,48,49,51–53,55,58,59,73–76]. The bridge rectifier consists of four diodes connected in a bridge (closed-loop) configuration, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The AC input is applied to two opposite corners of the bridge. At the same time, the DC output is delivered from the other two corners across a load resistor. In [38], three-phase full-wave diode rectifiers are employed. Diode bridge rectification is widely used since it is low-cost and does not require complex control methods to drive the circuit. As a result, diode bridge rectification is one of the most popular rectification techniques widely adopted in the literature [34,39,40,42–45,56,60,68,72,77–87].

The bridgeless AC-DC Cuk converter offers numerous advantages over traditional converter topologies. By replacing the diode bridge, these topologies reduce conduction losses, minimize voltage drops, and enhance overall system efficiency, particularly under light load conditions where traditional converters may experience significant losses. Bridgeless rectifiers use actively controlled switches such as MOSFETs instead of passive diodes, enabling synchronous rectification. This design approach results in fewer components, reduced thermal stress, and improved compactness. Petrovic et al. [47] utilized two MOSFETs in series with their body diodes to achieve rectification with one switch and one diode conducting per half cycle. R et al. [50] proposed a bridgeless Cuk PFC converter with symmetrical operation in both half cycles using MOSFET gate control. Other research, such as [26,63–65,88–90] replaced two diodes of a diode bridge with two MOSFET switches. On the other hand, [57,61,66,91,92] achieved bridgeless operation using a single MOSFET. In three-phase converter circuits [37,93] implemented three MOSFET switches for rectification instead of diodes. A Bridgeless single-switch Cuk PFC converter is shown in Fig. 4.

4.3. Isolation

Transformers play a crucial role in power converters by providing

Fig. 4. A Bridgeless single-switch Cuk PFC converter [91]. (The figure is used under the Creative Commons CC-BY license).

physical and electrical isolation between the input and output sides. It prevents direct current flow between the two sides and ensures safety and efficient operation. In contrast, non-isolated power converters lack this isolation, allowing current to flow through a single circuit from the input to the output. Based on the presence or absence of this isolation, AC-DC Cuk converters are classified into two categories: isolated and non-isolated.

Isolated power sources offer numerous benefits across various applications, such as level shifting, breaking ground loops, and ensuring compliance with safety standards. Safety is one of the significant reasons for using an isolated power converter, especially when handling high voltages such as those from AC mains in AC-DC converters. Isolation guarantees that the output remains separated from potentially hazardous input voltages. An evaluation of safety standards is necessary to ascertain the appropriate level of insulation for a particular application. Different insulation grades are available, including functional, basic, additional, and reinforced. Another key benefit of isolated converters is a floating output, allowing consistent voltage across output terminals without a fixed voltage reference relative to other circuit nodes. This flexibility provides voltage shifting or inversion relative to other circuit locations by connecting one terminal to a different circuit node. Circuits cited in references [26,27,29–31,41,48,58,60,68,84] are isolated. Similar to other power circuits, the parasitic capacitance in diodes can induce resonance with the resonant inductor. This effect, combined with the leakage inductance of the isolated transformer, causes some energy to remain trapped in the leakage inductance when the switch is turned off. Consequently, a significant voltage spike can be observed at the drain node of the power switch [78,81] proposed a system using three isolated Cuk converters arranged in a star connection offering fast transient response and a PF close to unity. A circuit topology for an isolated AC-DC Cuk converter is illustrated in Fig. 5. A comparative review of isolated single-phase AC-DC Cuk converters is demonstrated in Table 3.

Non-isolated AC-DC converters are known for their efficient voltage conversion without requiring electrical isolation between input and output. It makes them a reliable and simplified alternative to traditional isolated topologies. One of the significant features of the non-isolated AC-DC Cuk converter lies in its ability to operate efficiently in single-phase at DCM. This characteristic enables voltage-following behavior, eliminating the need for a dedicated current control loop. Additionally, its intrinsic design allows seamless implementation of input–output isolation, enhancing safety and versatility in diverse electrical systems. In reference [38,42,52,53,75,96,97], detailed implementations of non-isolated Cuk topologies are provided. Careful selection of magnetic component values is crucial for optimal performance and minimal input current ripple, which defines the converter's efficiency and reliability. This precision makes it ideal for applications prioritizing compact size, high performance, and flexibility. A non-isolated bridgeless Cuk PFC converter is illustrated in Fig. 6. A comparative review of non-isolated

single-phase AC-DC Cuk converters is shown in Table 4.

4.4. Power phase

Both the single-phase and three-phase AC-DC Cuk converters can be found in the literature. This section classifies the AC-DC Cuk converters based on the input AC phases.

The single-phase AC-DC PFC Cuk converter efficiently converts AC voltage to DC by transferring energy between the inductor and the capacitor components with improved power quality. It comprises essential elements such as an inductor (L), a capacitor (C), a power switch (MOSFET or transistor), and a diode. In reference [15,36,46,52–54,66,67,80,86,105] the authors used single-phase AC-DC converters. These converters are particularly beneficial in applications requiring voltage step-up or step-down with reduced ripple. They incorporate stages for smoothing, filtering, load regulation, and control through PWM and feedback loops. They are widely used in renewable energy systems, battery chargers, UPS, and motor drives as they can provide continuous input current and minimize output ripple. A single-phase AC-DC Cuk converter is illustrated in Fig. 7.

The three-phase Cuk converters are preferred in industrial and high-power applications due to their ability to deliver higher power output. They utilize three alternating current (AC) sources, each phase-shifted by 120 degrees, resulting in smoother power delivery and reduced voltage ripples. Although three-phase converters are more expensive and complex than single-phase converters, they offer several benefits, including higher load-handling capability and increased efficiency. Three-phase systems naturally facilitate balanced loads, ensuring uniform power consumption across all phases. This balanced distribution reduces stress on individual components and enhances system reliability. These converters are commonly used for PFC, which improves the overall system PF, promotes efficient energy utilization, and helps avoid penalties associated with poor power factors in commercial and industrial environments. Despite the intricacy of three-phase converter control, employing simpler control loops and minimizing sensor usage can enhance structural efficiency and reduce costs. Gangavarapu et al. [48] proposed a system based on only a straightforward voltage control loop for output voltage regulation that ensures reliability and robust control. Chunkag et al. [75] introduced a Cuk rectifier module by paralleling three-phase AC-DC converters using a power balance control technique. In another study, the same author, in collaboration with Kamnarn et al. [13], proposed a three-phase AC-DC converter using single-phase Cuk rectifier modules, resulting in PF correction and managed heavy step load changes under a DC-regulated output with the help of power balance control technique. According to Singh et al. [37], simple switching control can reduce the circuit complexity by allowing a single gate driver to operate all three switches in a three-phase AC-DC Cuk converter. Gangavarapu et al. [38] proposed a novel three-phase AC-DC PFC conversion system with limited components, resulting in

Fig. 5. Circuit topology for isolated AC-DC Cuk converter [94](The figure is used under the Creative Commons CC-BY license).

Table 3

A Comparative Review of Isolated single-phase AC-DC Cuk Converters (L = inductor; C = capacitor; S = active switch; D = diode; THDi = total harmonics distortion in input current; Tr = Transformer, η = efficiency, n = order of harmonics, N/A = non-available).

Ref	Rectifier Type	L	C	S	D	Tr	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[27]	Diode Bridge	2	4	1	5	1	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	50 W	0.9	15 %	N/A	Integration of magnetics within the Cuk converter designed for BLDC motor drives	+ Proposed an innovative design + Minimize motor torque ripples and improve efficiency. – It is not suitable for low-voltage BLDC motors.
[29]	Diode Bridge	3	4	1	5	1	DCM & CCM	Simulation	20.2 W	0.995	4.2 %	79.90 %	Modeling, simulation, and development of Cuk converter in DCM and CCM	+ High power quality – Requires complex control
[48]	Diode Bridge	6	7	3	15	1	DCM	Experimental	2 kW	0.999	4.06 %	95.10 %	Analysis and design of an isolated Cuk-based PFC converter	+ Eliminates the need for current sensors – It requires a large input inductor filter
[30]	Diode Bridge	3	3	1	5	1	DCM & CCM	Simulation	100 W	0.999	4.52 %	95.20 %	Improved power quality in AC-DC converters with HF transformer isolation.	+ High-frequency transformer isolation + Precise voltage regulation – Heavy volume requirements – Complex component selection
[73]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	1	1	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	100 W	1	4.20 %	93 %	Battery charger design for electric vehicles based on PF conversion	+ High output unity PF. + Fast charging capability. – Presence of harmonic currents.
[31]	Diode Bridge	2	3	1	5	1	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	4800 W	0.99	8.50 %	91 %	Implementation of digital double-loop	+ High power ratings + Increased control complexity – Challenges with load variation.
[13]	Diode Bridge	6	7	3	15	1	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	750 W	0.99	4 %	88 %	Fast dynamic response and PF correction in distributed power systems.	+ Fast dynamic response with a simple control strategy – Higher complexity compared to boost or flyback converters.
[33]	Diode Bridge /Three phase	6	4	3	15	3	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	N/A	0.99	2.61 %	87 %	Analysis and design of a three-phase PFC with current generation techniques under balanced and unbalanced supply conditions.	+ Achieves unity PF. + Wide load variations. – High current stresses and expensive.
[76]	Diode Bridge	2	3	1	5	1	CCM	Simulation	250 W	0.986	3.68 %	80 %	Parallel operation control of modular AC to DC converters via a communication bus.	+ Fast response to power requirements – Reliance on the clock signal for synchronization.
[26]	Bridgeless	2	5	2	1	2	DCM	Simulation	2.4 kW	0.99	5.81 %	N/A	A welding power supply requires a bridgeless Cuk converter with enhanced power quality.	+ Improved PF & reduced EMI – Increased spatter generation & stochastic welding process
[68]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	1	1	DCM	Simulation	100 W	Near unity	N/A	N/A	Analysis of Sepic and Cuk converters as PFP in DCM.	+ Efficient design with desired ripple value for input current – A slow feedback loop is required to avoid harmonic injection.
[63]	Bridgeless	5	6	2	3	1	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	200 W	1	2.10 %	95.83 %	Introduces a new bridgeless Cuk PFC converter with soft switching	+ Soft switching operation

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Ref	Rectifier Type	L	C	S	D	Tr	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[41]	Diode Bridge	4	5	3	7	1	CCM	Simulation	1 kW	N/A	4.60 %	N/A	Cuk converter-based LLC resonant converter for EVBC applications.	– High current stress on semiconductors + Reduces inrush current. – High input current peaks
[69]	Bridgeless	2	4	3	4	1	DCM	Experimental	900 W	1	2.80 %	$\cong 90\%$	Bridgeless Cuk converter for EV charger efficiency and power quality improvement	+ Improved efficiency, reduced THD, and unity PF – Increased complexity
[71]	Bridgeless	5	2	1	6	1	DCM	Simulation	N/A	unity	N/A	N/A	High-performance charging for electric two-wheelers and three-wheelers	+ Ripple-free charging + Simplified transformer design – Large circulating current
[95]	Diode Bridge	6	9	3	7	1	CCM	Simulation	1.5Kw	N/A	1.11 %	85 %	Evaluation of Cuk converter performance in various interleaved setups	– High EMI issues + Interleaved converters increase power density. – Complex circuit with higher component count.
[84]	Diode Bridge	3	4	1	5	1	CCM	Simulation	20 W	Up to 0.996	8.53 %	N/A	Simulation and design of high-frequency isolated AC-DC Cuk.	+ Low power rating. + Reduce THD – No internal current loops.

Fig. 6. Non-isolated bridgeless Cuk PFC converter[62](The figure is used under the Creative Commons CC-BY license).

fewer conduction losses and higher efficiency. Authors Kamnarn et al. [81] also proposed three-phase Cuk rectifier modules by using a three-star connected single-phase Cuk rectifier with the help of a power balance control technique. A three-phase Cuk-derived PFC converter is shown in Fig. 8.

5. Assessment of novel converter topologies

From the comparative review, some topologies outperform the other converters in several aspects. These prominent topologies provide comparable benefits, such as enhanced switching capabilities and improved current and voltage stress management. These benefits make them highly effective for various power applications, ensuring reliable and efficient power conversion with minimal energy loss. Some prominent topologies are illustrated in Figs. 9, 10, 11, and 12. The circuit diagrams and technical aspects of the converters are demonstrated in Table 5.

6. Technical comparison

To meet the requirements of modern industrial applications, an ideal industry-ready AC-DC converter must excel in various performance

aspects. For example, a high-quality AC-DC converter has a near unity PF, nearly zero input current THD, and almost 100 % conversion efficiency. To provide an overview of the development of Cuk topology over the years, it is essential to conduct a performance-wise comparative study of the existing literature. The reviewed Cuk converters are categorized into four power levels based on the power supplied to the resistive load, as illustrated in Fig. 13(a-d). The reported performance parameters of the converters (PF, %THD, %efficiency) from each paper are normalized for comparative analysis.

First, we compiled a set of selected converter topologies that have been practically implemented and experimentally validated. Since PF and efficiency are maximization parameters, they are normalized according to Eq. (1). In Eq. (1), the parameter, x_{npf} represents the normalized PF and efficiency, while x_{actual} , denotes the actual value of the parameter undergoing normalization. The subscripts (*min*) and (*max*) correspond to the minimum and maximum values of the respective parameters (PF or efficiency) within the dataset. On the other hand, since THD is a minimization parameter, it is normalized according to Eq. (2). In both equations, the normalized parameters are derived as absolute values.

$$x_{npf} = \frac{|x_{actual} - x_{min}|}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \quad (1)$$

$$x_{THD} = \frac{|x_{actual} - x_{max}|}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \quad (2)$$

6.1. Low power converters (THD < 5 %, efficiency > 85 %)

In Fig. 13(a), six Cuk topologies are compared for 0–100 W power levels, where the evaluation criteria required a THD of less than 5 % and an efficiency greater than 85 %. Among this category, Singh et al. [29] proposed a high-frequency AC-DC Cuk converter achieving near unity PF, 4.2 % THD at input current, and fell short on efficiency at 79.90 % for a 20.25 W load. The topology of Bodetto et al. [51] is on AC-DC PFC high-order converters for low-power applications, which not only satisfies the THD criterion with 1.26 % but also significantly exceeds the efficiency requirement at 94 %. Thangasankaran et al. [49]

Table 4

A Comparative Review of Isolated Single-Phase AC-DC Cuk Converters (L = inductor; C = capacitor; S = active switch; D = diode; THDi = total harmonics distortion in input current; Tr = Transformer, η = efficiency, n = order of harmonics, N/A = non-available).

Ref	Rectifier	L	C	S	D	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[47]	Bridgeless	1	2	2	4	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	N/A	1	N/A	98 %	Lyapunov analysis of AC-DC 'Cuk converter's operational modes.	+ Enables new control approaches for converters. - Limited experimental validation
[49]	Diode Bridge	3	3	2	6	DCM	Simulation	100 W	0.972	2.21 %	82.84 %	Analysis and design of AC-DC Interleaved negative output Cuk converter.	+ Improved PF with reduced THD - Challenges with output voltage accuracy
[74]	Diode Bridge	4	5	4	4	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	3.7 kW	99.3	< 5 %	96 %	Bidirectional AC-DC converter for battery integration	+ Easy installation and high efficiency - Complex control system
[50]	Bridgeless	3	3	1	5	DCM	Simulation	N/A	0.99	0.14 %	N/A	Bridgeless Cuk PFC with regulated output voltage	+ Reduced conduction losses with better thermal management - Challenges to stability
[51]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	1	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	45 W	1	1.26 %	94 %	Design of AC-DC PFC converters for low-power applications.	+ Efficient drivers for low-power applications. - Harmful harmonic distortion in input line current waveform
[98]	Bridgeless	2	2	1	4	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.989	8.60 %	N/A	Closed loop Cuk AC to DC converter performance and power quality evaluation.	+ Closed loop Cuk converter with regulated voltage. - Passive filters are bulky & costly.
[75]	Diode Bridge	12	13	6	30	DCM	Simulation	1.5 kW	0.99	1.30 %	88 %	Control technique for paralleling three-phase AC-DC converter modules	+ Modular converter architecture - High voltage stress
[52]	Diode Bridge	3	2	1	5	DCM	Comparison	N/A	0.995	4.40 %	87 %	Analysis of PFC converter using close loop Cuk topology	+ Improved PF, better voltage regulation, reduced input current THD - High voltage stresses
[53]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	CCM	Simulation	20.25 W	0.997	4.48 %	82.4 %	Cuk AC-DC converter with hysteresis current and voltage loop	+ High design flexibility with different dc-bus voltage levels - Increased complexity in control mechanisms due to multi-level operation
[54]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	DCM	Simulation	2 kW	0.998	3.24 %	N/A	PF improvement in vector-controlled PMSM drive system	+ Isolation in PMSM drive - Increased losses in utility line.
[88]	Bridgeless	2	3	2	2	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	500 W	0.999	3.56 %	N/A	Bridgeless Cuk converter-fed BLDC motor drive for air conditioning system	+ Cost-effective drive, wide speed control range. - Higher stresses on the PFC converter switch.
[55]	Diode Bridge	2	1	1	5	DCM	Simulation	0.816 kW	0.999	2.22 %	N/A	Voltage control and PF correction in PMBLDCM for air-conditioners	+ Offers high efficiency and wide speed range. - Power quality

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Ref	Rectifier	L	C	S	D	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[34]	Diode Bridge	4	5	1	6	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.994	0.04 %	95 %	Analysis of novel Cuk converter with PFC for power quality improvement	reduces, high harmonic distortion + Low THD with near unity PF – bulky passive filtering and additional DC-DC converter needed
[99]	Bridgeless	2	2	2	4	CCM	Simulation	33.6 W	N/A	N/A	79.60 %	Construction of AC-DC converters from DC-DC converters without input rectifiers	+ Eliminates zero-crossing distortions. + Suitable for aircraft systems. – Complicated circuits. – Four quadrant switches might be required.
[100]	Bridgeless	2	2	1	1	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	253.05 W	N/A	N/A	98 %	Highly efficient MPPT algorithm design for PV systems using fuzzy logic	+ Improved dynamic response and steady-state performance of PV systems. – Slower response time and significant overshoot
[35]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.997	3.33 %	N/A	AC-DC Cuk converter for LED lighting system	+ Unity PF and low current distortion. – Current and voltage sensors are required.
[46]	Bridgeless	3	5	2	5	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.802	54.94 %	99.99 %	High step-up converters for efficient energy transformation	+ High step-up ratio with reduced THD. – Increased system cost
[91]	Bridgeless	3	2	1	5	DCM	Simulation	100 W	N/A	N/A	N/A	Circulating current elimination and maximum current stress reduction in converters.	+ Circulating current elimination. – High output voltage ripple
[49]	Diode Bridge	5	4	2	6	DCM	Simulation	100 W	0.9901	1.42 %	85.92 %	Analysis and design of AC-DC Interleaved negative output Cuk converter	+ Improved PF, reduced THD, high efficiency – Injected current harmonics
[57]	Bridgeless	3	3	1	5	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	150 W	0.99	2.66 %	96.20 %	Performance analysis of bridgeless Cuk rectifier with positive output voltage	+ Low current ripple – Discontinuous output current
[36]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.999	1.59 %	91.20 %	Analysis, design, and evaluation of a 1.5 kW PFC	+ Improved PF, reduced THD – Issues with injected current harmonics and poor PF
[58]	Diode Bridge	6	7	3	15	DCM	Simulation	750	>0.99	< 5 %	88 %	Comparative analysis of Flyback and Cuk converters for power quality improvement.	+ Improved power quality, reduced THD with unity PF. – Increased complexity and higher cost due to multiple stages
[96]	Diode Bridge	3	6	7	2	N/A	Simulation	1.2 kW	N/A	N/A	N/A	Integration of Cuk and SWISS converters for power generation	+ High power generation with continuous current flow. – Lagging current in PV system.

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Ref	Rectifier	L	C	S	D	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[37]	Bridgeless	6	4	3	3	DCM Simulation CCM & DCM- Experimental	Experimental & Simulation	200 W- DCM 576- CCM	N/A	N/A	95.18 % 90.14 %	Three-phase AC-DC converter for PMSG-based wind energy conversion system.	+ Efficient, simple control – Requires sensing of generator voltage and current.
[59]	Diode Bridge	6	6	1	8	DCM	Simulation	N/A	0.98	3.40 %	90 %	Transformer design parameters and power balance calculations.	+ Simplifies control design. – Reduces switching losses
[60]	Diode Bridge	2	4	1	5	DCM	Simulation and Hardware	4 W and 20.25 W	HW-0.98 & 0.99	4.50 %	79.9	Efficiency improvement in single-switch AC-DC converters	+ Low cost and simple control scheme. – Minimal line current distortion
[59]	Bridgeless	3	3	1	5	DCM	Simulation	200w	N/A	low	N/A	Operation and control system of BPFC Cuk converter	+ Fast steady state. + Low output voltage ripples. – Nonlinear operation. – Complex control.
[61]	Bridgeless	3	3	1	5	DCM	Simulation	150 W	0.996	2.66 %	96.20 %	Efficiency improvement and simplified control circuit design	+ Positive output voltage – Increased conduction losses.
[38]	Diode Bridge	6	5	3	6	CCM & DCM	Hardware & Simulation	1000 & 2000 W	0.999	3.915 %	93.97 % & 94.11 %	Control scheme for sinusoidal input current and regulated output voltage	+ Reduced components with simple control. – Requires high current
[62]	Bridgeless	4	3	2	4	DCM	Simulation	18 W	N/A	2 %	93	Analysis and design of PFC Cuk converter	+ Low current ripple – Limited to low-power applications.
[77]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	1	DCM	Hardware & Simulation	N/A	nearly 1	2 %	N/A	Fast-response controller design for Cuk converters in DCVM	+ Fast dynamic response with improved transient response – Slow reaction to load changes
[39]	Diode Bridge	8	5	4	9	CCM & CCM	Simulation	N/A	N/A	4.5 %	N/A	Control of SRM drive with PFC converter for power quality enhancement	+ Improved power quality and low cost – High torque ripple and noise.
[64]	Bridgeless	2	2	3	3	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	100 W	0.996	0.5 mA/w	93.50 %	Implementing a bridgeless Cuk PFC with reduced conduction losses	+ Reduced conduction losses. – high component count
[89]	Bridgeless	2	3	1	2	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	1kw	0.9994	3rd order 3.49 %	94 %	Reduced component count for on-board EV charging.	+ Improved power density simple control operation. – Floating terminal.
[90]	Bridgeless	2	4	4	5	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	125.5 W	N/A	10 %	86.50 %	Novel Cuk-based bridgeless rectifier for wireless power transfer system.	+ Wide power modulation range. – Large output ripple.
[65]	Bridgeless	2	3	2	4	DCM	Experimental & Simulation	300 W	0.998	4.40 %	93.58 %	Switched inductor network for high voltage gain rectifiers.	+ High step-down voltage gain. – Higher current stress in conventional PFC rectifiers
[93]	Bridgeless	6	12	6	–	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	1 kW	0.998	6.68 %	92 %	Passive damping optimization in integrated-magnetics-based differential-mode Cuk rectifier.	+ Enhanced power density – Modest efficiency reduction at 1 kW Cuk rectifier.

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Ref	Rectifier	L	C	S	D	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[101]	Diode Bridge	4	2	1	7	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	N/A	0.99	2.88 %	N/A	PFC converter implantation with regulated output voltage	+ High efficiency and simple design. – Bulk capacitor variation
[66]	Bridgeless	3	3	1	5	DCM	Simulation	N/A	0.99	8.2 % & 10.4 %	N/A	Control scheme design for bridgeless Cuk converter	+ Tracks reference voltage effectively. – Complicated structure
[40]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	1	CCM	Simulation	72 W	0.99	6.58 %	N/A	Power quality improvement in AC-DC Cuk converter	+ High PF – Requires conditioning technique
[67]	Bridgeless	3	4	2	2	DCM	Simulation	N/A	0.97	3 %	88 %	Bridgeless AC-DC Modified Cuk Converter with PFC scheme analysis.	+ Minimized power loss with improved efficiency. – High power applications limitation.
[56]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	DCM	Experimental	64.9 W	0.984	4.7 %	95 %	Reducing output filtering capacitance	+ Long-life LED driver with reduced output filtering. – Decrease luminous efficacy of LEDs.
[78]	Diode Bridge	3	6	1	5	DCM	Simulation	1018 W	0.944	N/A	93.80 %	Integrated AC-DC system for LED with single switch rectifier	+ Efficient LED driver – Ripple factor variations
[92]	Bridgeless	4	3	1	5	DCM	Simulation	N/A	0.99	4 %	93 %	PF improvement and low input current THD	+ Improved PF with low input current THD. – Absence of input-side filtering
[79]	Diode Bridge	2	2	2	6	CCM	Simulation	1 kW	0.9942	7.61 %	89.30 %	AC-DC Cuk converter based on Three-State Switching Cell	+ high power quality – Less efficiency
[42]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	5	CCM & DCM	Simulation	100 W	0.77	40.99 %	N/A	Dynamic PF correction using Cuk converter in AC-DC conversion	+ Improved PF, with reduced current harmonics – Fixed capacitors and inductors.
[80]	Diode Bridge	6	5	1	6	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.994	12 %	95 %	Single-phase Cuk AC-DC converter performance and efficiency comparison	+ High efficiency – Small filter required
[102]	Diode Bridge	4	5	1	10	CCM	Simulation	N/A	0.96	1.00 %	87.50 %	Analysis of AC-DC Cuk converters for variable loads	+ Efficient variable load performance. – High voltage stresses – Bulky input filter
[81]	Diode Bridge Three-Phase	6	7	3	15	CCM	Simulation	1.5 kW	N/A	N/A	N/A	Power balance control technique for improved dynamic response and simplicity	+ Fast transient response. – Large ripple in output voltage
[83]	Diode Bridge	2	1	1	6	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	89 W	0.98	21.0 %	85.5 %	Design of high-PF offline LED driver with Cuk-based pre-regulator.	+ Extended lifetime. – Low efficiency
[43]	Diode Bridge	1	1	1	8	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	9.5 kW	0.97	2.30 %	N/A	Two switch three phase Cuk regulated rectifier circuit analysis.	+ Fewer components, + Simplified control – Output voltage feedback control
[103]	Bridgeless	3	3	2	3	DCM	Simulation	65 W	N/A	N/A	N/A	Reducing power switch current stress and low losses also	+ Fewer conduction losses – Reduces power

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Ref	Rectifier	L	C	S	D	Operating Mode	Evaluation Type	Power Level	PF	THDi	η	Study focus	Pros (+) & Cons (-)
[104]	Bridgeless	4	3	4	1	CCM	Simulation	110 W	N/A	N/A	N/A	improved thermal management. Novel hybrid converters for AC and DC loads for improved gain.	switch current stress. + Improved output voltage gain. - Limitation of current supply.
[97]	Bridgeless	5	5	2	4	DCM	Simulation	408 W	0.99	2.80 %	N/A	SRM drive with dual output voltages.	+ Cost-effective with reduced size. - Peak voltage stress 500 V and current stress 20A.
[45]	Diode Bridge Three Phase	6	4	3	15	CCM	Simulation	500 W	N/A	N/A	N/A	Parallel AC-DC converters using Cuk topology with power balance control technique for tight DC bus voltage.	+ Current sharing. - High cost, size, and weight.
[62]	Bridgeless	4	3	2	4	DCM	Simulation	18 W	N/A	below 2 %	N/A	Bridgeless Cuk PFC rectifiers for PF correction.	+ Low current ripple. - Limited to low-power applications
[85]	Diode Bridge	3	2	1	6	CCM & DCM	Hardware & Simulation	N/A	0.98–1	N/A	N/A	PF correction in AC/DC-DC converters for electric vehicles	+ High efficiency with soft switching capability. - Copper, iron, and conduction losses.
[86]	Diode Bridge	4	5	1	13	CCM	Experimental & Simulation	N/A	0.998	2.41 %	N/A	Improved power quality under varying duty ratios and switching frequency	+ High voltage gain. - Large output filter needed
[72]	Diode Bridge	3	4	1	5	DCM	Simulation	N/A	unity	4.28 %	N/A	Converter design for E-bike charging application	+ Efficient battery charging system. - Increase complexity - Simulation dependence.
[44]	Diode Bridge	3	4	1	5	CCM	Simulation	20 W	0.982–0.996	8.53 % & 10.65 %	N/A	Design and simulation of high-frequency isolated AC-DC Cuk Converter.	+ Improve PF & reduce THD. - Harmonic distortion.
[87]	Diode Bridge	2	2	1	6	CCM	Simulation	45 W	N/A	6 %	N/A	Power quality improvement and variable frequency control in HBLED drivers.	+ Low THD and good power quality. - Harmonic distortion near zero.

demonstrated superior performance, achieving a THD of 2.21 %, well within the required criteria of 5 %. The diode bridge Cuk converter by Yadav et al. [73] achieves a unity PF with an efficiency of 93 %. In contrast, the bridgeless Cuk converter by Lin et al. [64] improved the efficiency to 93.5 % with a PF of 0.996 for a 100 W load, both meeting the criteria. Fig. 13(b) compares another 6 Cuk topologies on the 101–500 W spectrum, each demonstrating different performance metrics. Among them, Kanthaphayao et al. [76] proposed an AC to DC Cuk Converter circuit, achieving a PF of 0.986 with 3.68 % THD and 80 % efficiency for a 250 W load. While the THD is well within the 5 % limit, efficiency falls short of 85 %. In contrast, Valan Rajkumar et al. [57] presented a bridgeless topology for a 150 W application with 96.20 % efficiency and 2.66 % THD, comfortably meeting both criteria because it uses six active circuit components, which results in a 0.99 PF. The proposed Bridgeless Cuk PFC Converter of Shameli et al. [63] excelled with a unity PF and 2.10 % THD, setting the benchmark for THD in this range. However, the exact efficiency was not specified. Babaei et al. [65] proposed a 300 W AC to DC Bridgeless Cuk converter with a 0.998 PF,

Fig. 7. Single Phase AC-DC Cuk Converter [105]. (The figure is used under the Creative Commons CC-BY license).

Fig. 8. Three-phase Cuk-derived PFC converter [81].

Fig. 9. Bridgeless Cuk PFC converter [64].

4.40 % THD, and 93.58 % efficiency—satisfying all criteria. Anand et al. [97] proposed a Cuk converter for 408 W load applications to feed a switched reluctance motor (SRM) drive, achieving a notable 2.8 % THD and a PF 0.99. For 100 W loads, Singh et al. [88] and Kanthaphayao et al. [45] proposed a bridgeless Cuk converter. Among them, Singh et al. [88] outperformed with a 0.999 PF and 3.56 % THD, meeting the thresholds, while Yang et al. [61] attained 0.9961 PF, 2.66 % THD, and 96.20 % efficiency for a 150 W application, also satisfying the criteria.

The performance of different Cuk converter topologies for loads

ranging from 501 to 1000 W is contrasted in Fig. 13(c). Among them, the proposed converter of Kamnarn et al. [13] achieved a PF of 0.99, an input current of THD 4 %, and an efficiency of 88 %. The power quality improved in the Cuk topology by R. Kushwaha [69] – a unity PF was achieved for the EV charger for 900 W load with 2.80 % THD. The 94 % efficiency of Dutta et al. [89] is the highest of this range, supporting at most a 1000 W load. Based on the Three-state switching cell, Pacheco et al. [79] designed an interesting Cuk topology with two solid-state switches and six diodes, which resulted in the input current THD being increased to 7 %, maintaining 0.99 PF and 89.30 % efficiency while supporting 1000 W load. For 1000 W applications, the proposed bridgeless topology of Gangavarapu et al. [38] achieved a maximum of 93.97 efficiency. However, it also provides 3.91 % THD and 0.99 PF.

6.1.2. High power converters (THD < 3 %, efficiency > 92 %)

The performance of the converters compatible with the above 1000 W load range is illustrated in Fig. 13(d). Among this category, Chunkag et al. [75] proposed a power balance control technique-based AC to DC Cuk converter achieving a 1.30 % THD but with a marginal efficiency of 88 % with a PF of 0.99 for 1500 W load. Newton et al. [106] proposed that the converter achieved the lowest THD at 1.11 % but struggled with efficiency, recording only 85 %. Two converters, proposed by

Fig. 10. High-gain Cuk PFC rectifiers [65] (The figure is used under the Creative Commons CC-BY license).

Fig. 11. Soft switching bridgeless PFC Cuk converter[63].

Fig. 12. Single-phase bridgeless Cuk converter [89].

Gangavarapu et al. [48] and Singh et al. [54], achieved efficiencies of 96.56 % and THD values of 4.06 % and 3.24 %, respectively, only partially meeting the high-power criteria and near unity PF in the above 2000 W spectrum. For a 3700 W load, Kroics et al. [74] reported 96 % efficiency, which is the highest in this range. Additionally, it provides acceptable input current THD with a near-unity PF. Abedin et al. [43] proposed the maximum load of 9500 W AC to DC Cuk converter topology, achieving 2.30 % THD with a PF of 0.97, marking it as one of the few configurations that meet both efficiency and THD benchmarks.

7. Technical issues and challenges

7.1. Integration with new energy systems

In light of global decarbonization goals, it is essential to consider

Table 5
Prominent topologies of AC-DC Cuk Converter.

Prominent Topologies	Advantages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple Circuit Structure • High PF • Reduced Conduction loss • Enhanced PFC capability and higher efficiency than the pseudo-totem-pole bridgeless Cuk • Satisfies IEC 61000-3-2 Class D limits
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on switched inductor network • High step-down voltage gains with a higher duty cycle • Lower current stress
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides soft switching operation • Achieves low input THD without any input filter
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lower Voltage Stress • Reduced switching loss • Ensures easy thermal management

Fig. 13. (a): Cuk topologies for 0–100 W power level. Fig. 13(b): Cuk topologies on the 101–500 W spectrum. Fig. 13(c): Performance parameters of the Cuk topologies supporting 501–1000 W load. Fig. 13(d): Performance of the converters compatible with the above 1000 W load.

how AC–DC Cuk converters can serve emerging renewable energy and “new energy” scenarios. For example, Cuk converters can be incorporated into solar PV, wind turbines, hybrid microgrids [107], and electric vehicle (EV) charging systems. Their continuous input and output current characteristics make them attractive for interfacing with distributed DC sources and batteries, while their high efficiency and simple control suit lightweight EV or fuel-cell applications [108]. However, challenges arise due to the wide voltage variability of renewable sources (requiring high step-up or step-down ratios) and the inherently inverted output of the classic Cuk topology (often necessitating an additional stage for positive DC output). These issues must be addressed for Cuk converters to be viable in grid-tied inverters, PV/storage systems, and bidirectional EV/battery interfaces. In this context, modified high-gain Cuk topologies and wide-band gap devices have been proposed to overcome parasitic losses and improve efficiency for renewable applications [67,106].

7.2. Regional and Industry-Specific constraints

Another technical issue is that converter design requirements vary by region and industry. Local efficiency and safety standards (e.g., IEC, UL, DOE regulations), electromagnetic compatibility limits, operating environment (temperature, humidity, altitude), and cost targets differ across markets. For instance, designs intended for developing regions may prioritize low cost and robustness to harsh climates. In contrast, converters for advanced industrial markets may emphasize ultra-high efficiency and full compliance with strict emissions regulations. These market-specific constraints influence component selection (e.g., inductor/generator sizing and cooling) and control strategy. To date,

few reviews have addressed how Cuk converter topologies must be adapted to such diverse regulatory and environmental conditions, a gap in the current state of the art.

Our recent analysis of AC-DC Cuk converter topologies has further identified various technical concerns that must be addressed. While acknowledging the absence of a flawless converter design, we have identified particular difficulties and constraints that affect the effectiveness and efficiency of Cuk AC-DC converters. Table 6. compiles the significant technical problems and challenges recorded in the literature, serving as a foundation for subsequent discussion and enhancement.

8. Future aspects

8.1. Cuk converters for renewable and green applications

Future research should explore Cuk converter topologies optimized for renewable energy systems and sustainable applications. It includes multi-port or hybrid converters that integrate photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, batteries, and EV batteries in a single stage, as well as bidirectional Cuk designs for vehicle-to-grid (V2G) or energy storage systems [104,107]. Investigating high-frequency, high-gain Cuk variants (using GaN/SiC switches) could improve efficiency and power density in solar/battery installations. Advanced control methods (e.g., adaptive MPPT and grid-support functionalities) should be developed to ensure stable operation under variable renewable conditions [100]. Overall, aligning Cuk converter research with carbon-reduction goals means prioritizing renewable integration and bidirectional storage applications.

Table 6
Technical problems and difficulties recorded in the literature.

Issue	Description	Real-World Application	Impact Analysis
High conduction and magnetic losses	The Cuk converters need additional inductors and capacitors compared to the buck or boost topology. These elements increase conduction, magnetic losses, and power dissipation, especially when operating at low output voltages and high currents. [29,49,53,76,99].	Renewable energy systems (solar PV), EV charging stations, and microgrids.	It reduces efficiency, excess heat generation, and higher cooling requirements.
Electromagnetic Interference	Some Cuk converters produce substantial high-frequency noise during switching actions, necessitating sophisticated filtering methods to meet Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) standards. EMI contributes to the intricacy and expense of the design and controllers. [49,63].	Smart grids, industrial automation, and EV power electronics.	It disrupts communication networks and sensitive electronics, increasing costs for filtering.
Output Voltage Stability	Achieving a stable output voltage can be challenging due to ripple and slowly changing DC levels, affecting sensitive electronic equipment performance. Additionally, rapid changes in load resulted in transient spikes and dips in output voltage, challenging the converter's ability to maintain a stable output. Different PID-based and advanced control algorithms were applied to optimize performance [29,49,83,109].	Off-grid solar applications, smart homes, and critical industrial systems.	Fluctuations compromise the performance of sensitive devices, risking data loss and equipment damage.
Higher Component Count	Additional components like capacitors, inductors, and heat sinks are needed to manage heat. EMI increases the cost and size of the converter, making the design less compact and more expensive [13,29,48,58,73,81,93].	Distributed energy storage systems and hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs).	It makes designs bulkier, reduces compactness, and increases manufacturing costs.
Semiconductor Device Stress	High switching frequencies and current demands can stress components, reducing their reliability and lifespan. This is a common issue in high-power and high-frequency converter designs [29]. High-stress levels necessitated the use of robust components, which increased costs and design complexity [29,41,83,110].	High-power grid-tied converters and large-scale energy storage.	Increases the risk of early component failure, leading to higher maintenance costs.
Switching Losses	High switching losses in DCM and the need for high-frequency operation can reduce overall efficiency, especially in lighter load conditions. [38,62,65].	Smart inverters for solar panels, EV chargers, and UPS systems.	Reduced efficiency affects energy savings and system reliability.
Control Complexity	Achieving high PF and low THD requires complex control strategies, often involving advanced control algorithms and precise tuning of system parameters. [27,30,49].	Microgrid synchronization, industrial motor drives, and renewable energy systems.	Complexity raises computational demands and costs, complicating real-time control.
Integration with Renewable Energy Systems	Modern renewable sources (solar PV, wind, fuel cells) provide variable DC outputs whose voltage fluctuates with environmental conditions [107]. Achieving a stable, higher DC voltage from such low-voltage sources often requires very high step-up gain, which is typically achieved with multi-stage or coupled-inductor Cuk topologies. The converter must also support maximum power point tracking (MPPT) and grid/microgrid interfacing, adding control complexity. For example, an interleaved Cuk converter has been demonstrated to efficiently extract power from a wave-energy source and seamlessly interface with an AC grid [49,82,95,111].	Stand-alone or grid-connected PV/wind systems, battery-storage microgrids, and renewable-powered EV chargers.	High step-up requirements add component count (inductors, switches) and design complexity.
Regional and Market-Specific Constraints	Cuk converter designs must satisfy diverse regional regulations and industry standards. Different markets impose distinct safety, quality, and grid-connection requirements (e.g., North American UL/CSA vs. European IEC/VDE standards, IEEE 1547 vs. IEC 62109 grid codes). Industrial sectors add further constraints. For example, telecommunications require high-reliability –48 V systems, automotive demands ISO 26262-level safety and wide temperature range, and consumer electronics enforce RoHS/EMC compliance. Converters may need hardening for local environmental conditions (extreme heat, cold, humidity) and certification testing.	PV inverters (which must meet region-specific grid codes), EV and battery chargers (automotive or stationary standards), telecom/IT power supplies, and industrial drives. For instance, a globally sold PV inverter must be certified to UL 1741/IEEE 1547 (USA) and IEC 62109/VDE (Europe).	Satisfying multiple standards typically increases cost and design time. Designers face trade-offs like adding EMI filters or magnetic isolation to meet EMC/safety rules, which raises losses and component count. Similarly, ruggedizing converters for harsh climates (larger heat sinks, higher-grade parts) improves reliability but adds weight and expense.

8.2. Customized designs for regional and regulatory needs

Future work should also address the diverse requirements of different industries and regions. Researchers should develop design frameworks that allow Cuk converters to be tailored for specific markets.

For example, converters that meet stringent European efficiency directives or that use low-cost components suitable for emerging economies. It may involve lifecycle and sustainability analyses (e.g., materials recycling, eco-friendly components), compliance with regional grid codes, and performance optimization in extreme environments.

Table 7
Key aspects and future opportunities of Cuk converter topologies.

Aspects	Description
High-Efficiency Industrial Drives	Industrial applications can utilize advanced control algorithms to enhance motor performance, decrease energy usage, and minimize torque fluctuations. Cuk converters facilitate regenerative braking by capturing and harnessing energy during deceleration, enhancing the system's overall efficiency.
Electric Grid Infrastructure	Applying Cuk converters in power conditioning systems aims to achieve voltage regulation and enhance power quality. Dynamic control of grid parameters can be achieved through integration with FACTS (Flexible Alternating Current Transmission Systems) devices—an investigation into Cuk converter-based solutions for grid modernization and the implementation of smart grid applications. The objective is to design fault-tolerant Cuk converter architectures that will improve the reliability and resilience of electric grid infrastructure.
Energy Storage Systems	Cuk converters in energy storage systems enable efficient battery charging and discharging. Integrating renewable energy sources like solar and wind into the power grid to stabilize and reduce peak demand. Finding bidirectional Cuk converter configurations that optimize energy transfer between energy storage systems and the grid. Investigation into Cuk converter-based grid-scale energy storage solutions to enable large-scale renewable energy implementation.
Cuk Converters in Renewable/Low-Carbon Systems	Cuk topologies entail clean-energy applications, such as multiport PV–battery–wind converters, grid-tied EV chargers, and bidirectional energy storage interfaces. Emphasize high-gain and wide-bandgap implementations to meet renewable system requirements (efficiency, power density) [107].
Improved Dynamic Response	Cuk AC-DC converters optimize dynamic response by reducing conversion stages, enabling faster energy transfer. This feature is precious in applications that require quick adjustments and the ability to respond to changing load conditions.
Localization and Sustainability of Designs	Cuk converters can be further evolved to facilitate regional market needs, e.g., cost-sensitive layouts for emerging economies, compliance with local efficiency/EMC regulations, and materials/lifecycle considerations. Research should include design-for-manufacturing (accounting for production volumes) and region-specific environmental stress testing.
Potential new applications	<p>Medical Devices: Integrating Cuk converters into medical equipment can guarantee stable and precise power delivery, improving the performance, reliability, and safety of critical devices such as MRI and X-ray machines.</p> <p>Home Appliances: By integrating Cuk converters into household appliances (i.e., charging household batteries), energy efficiency and performance are enhanced, energy consumption is reduced, costs are lowered, and the user experience is improved through high quality power usages [108].</p> <p>Grid-tied Inverters: Cuk converters integrated into grid-tied solar inverters optimize power conversion efficiency, enhance grid stability, maximize energy extraction, minimize power conversion losses, and ensure grid stability and dependability.</p> <p>Aerospace: Cuk converters provide aircraft systems with lightweight and efficient power conversion, enhancing fuel efficiency and range by optimizing design and control algorithms to minimize weight, size, and power losses.</p>

Modeling studies and hardware prototypes should explicitly consider production volume effects (since cost scales with manufacturing volume) and local constraints. By incorporating these considerations into converter design, future Cuk topologies can better satisfy various application scenarios' cost, regulatory, and sustainability demands.

From extensive literature research, it is noticeable that the existing AC-DC Cuk converters are reaching saturation and improvement. PFC-type Cuk converters have achieved near unity PF, while the others have achieved %THD as low as 0.99 % and efficiency as high as 99 %. At present, researchers are more focused on application-oriented improvements. The primary objective is to enhance the performance of these converters for specific purposes by tackling distinct operational obstacles and incorporating sophisticated control methods to maximize their effectiveness in diverse real-world scenarios, including electric vehicle charging, renewable energy systems, and high-efficiency industrial drives. The purpose of this shift is to utilize the well-established efficiency of Cuk converters in specific, practical situations. Table 7. demonstrates some of the key findings from the review, which require further research.

9. Conclusion

This review has introduced a four-criterion classification framework for AC–DC Cuk converter topologies, systematically categorizing designs by rectification method, conduction mode, isolation scheme, and phase configuration. This structured taxonomy clarifies the diverse literature, enabling direct comparisons among variants and highlighting how recent innovations extend beyond those in earlier surveys. Synthesizing data from the surveyed works, the review establishes performance benchmarks: for example, bridgeless Cuk configurations consistently achieve the highest conversion efficiencies due to reduced conduction losses. These insights confirm that modern designs, such as fully controlled multiphase and hybrid topologies, address historical power factor correction and component stress challenges.

In addition to classification and benchmarking, the review distills practical guidelines for EV charging and renewable energy systems. By

mapping topological features to application requirements (e.g., power level, isolation needs, and efficiency goals), it recommends design choices tailored to specific use cases. For instance, high-power EV on-board chargers that demand unity power factor and galvanic isolation are best served by fully isolated, high-frequency Cuk variants with integrated PFC. In contrast, low-voltage renewable inverters can favor non-isolated or bridgeless designs to maximize efficiency and simplify hardware under variable loads. These guidelines translate the review's comparative analysis into actionable insights, bridging the gap between theoretical converter studies and real-world power electronics design.

Importantly, this review fills gaps left by prior literature. Earlier surveys [15,16] provided broad overviews of Cuk converter variants but lacked a unified taxonomy and application-focused assessment. For example, references [15] and [16] did not offer a comprehensive classification, and [15] did not explicitly link topologies to emerging use cases. By explicitly connecting identified limitations of past works to the proposed classification and results, the present study uniquely integrates taxonomy, performance benchmarking, and industry relevance. This holistic perspective synthesizes state-of-the-art more deeply than past reviews and charts a more straightforward path for the future development of AC-DC Cuk converters.

To sum up, the key findings of this review, including the structured 4-criteria taxonomy, the identification of bridgeless designs as high-efficiency configurations, and the application-driven design guidelines, provide a concise yet thorough summary of current knowledge. The review establishes a comprehensive framework for Cuk converter selection and paves the way for optimized implementations in sustainable energy conversion applications.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Istiaq Ahmed: Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Asif Imtiaz Alvy:** Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Irfan Rahman:** Writing – original draft, Software. **Md. Abdullah Al Hossain:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Showrov Rahman:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Abdullah Al-Hysam:** Writing

– review & editing, Resources. **Abdur Razzak**: Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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